

A STUDY OF VILLAGE DAIRY COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES IN GUJARAT STATE

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Abstract:

Primary village Co-operative Society: An Anand Pattern village dairy cooperative society (DCS) is formed by milk producers. Any producer can become a DCS member by buying a share and committing to sell milk only to the society. Each DCS has a milk collection centre where members take milk every day. Each member's milk is tested for quality with payments based on the percentage of fat and SNF. At the end of each year, a portion of the DCS profits is used to pay each member a patronage bonus based on the quantity of milk poured. The present study was conducted to evaluate the status of VDCS in Gujarat state. The study covered all districts of the state and information was collected by using questionnaire. After analyzing the collected data it could be concluded that Most of VDCS are registered and have Young and literate employees and are well equipped with ICT facility available in terms of computers. However, few VDCS are not ISO certified and do not have Bulk Milk Chilling (BMC) facility and in the era of women empowerment, the issue of less female representation in management of VDCS should be addressed. Issues like capacity building and Training on Record keeping should be looked into. Overall it can be said that the VDCS of the state have contributed significantly to the development of Dairy Sector in the state

Key Words: Village Dairy Cooperative Societies, Gujarat Dairy, Dairy Business & Amul Pattern

1. Introduction:

Indian Dairy Sector:

The Indian Dairy cooperatives structure has a huge contribution in raising the milk production in the country upto approximately 146 million tonnes in the year 2014-15 from a meagre milk production 17 million tonnes in the year 1951. The per capita availability of milk in the country has increased to 340 g /day (GCMMF Annual Report 2015-16). Further, milk is the largest agricultural crop in India with market value exceeding Rs 4 lakh crore per annum and the milk group contributes the highest to the total output of our agricultural sector, surpassing the output value of wheat, rice and oilseeds.

S.No	Milk Marketing Channels
1	Producer —————D Consumer
2	Producer ———D Vendor —————D Consumer
3	Producer ———D Halwaii —————D Consumer
4	Producer ———D Vendor —————D Processor ———D Consumer
5	Producer ———D Middlemen/Milk Producers Cooperative Society —D Milk Plant ———D Consumer

Gujarat has around 18,536 village level cooperative societies, which have 33,65,442 dairy farmers. As per data available for year 2013-14, there were around 2641 Women Dairy Cooperative societies, around 4233 societies had installed Bulk Milk

coolers (BMC), around 11,814 societies had Automated Milk Collection Systems (AMCS). This numbers indicate the trust and involvement of dairy farmers in the cooperative set up and are the reason for continuous improvement in the quality of raw milk and final products of the cooperatives.

2. Methodology:

The study was being spread over the entire state and primary data was collected by way of a Questionnaire. The study covered all 26 Districts of Gujarat state, 227 talukas and further, three villages were selected from each taluka. In total 681 villages from the state were selected and data was collected VDCS.

3. Results and Findings:

(a). VDCS Registration:

VDCS Registered or Not	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Registered	307	85%
Unregistered	56	15%
Total respondents	363	100%

Around 85% of village dairy cooperatives were registered.

(b). VDCS ISO Certification:

Type of VDCS	No. of Respondents	Percentage
ISO Certified	195	54%
Non- ISO certified	166	46%
Total respondents	363	100%

As seen from the above table around 54% of the VDCS were ISO certified.

(c). VDCS Years of Existence:

Years of Existence	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
<10 years	94	29%
11 to 20 years	50	16%
21 to 30 years	34	11%
31 to 40 years	81	25%
41 to 50 years	39	12%
51 to 60 years	21	7%
> 60 years	2	1%
Total	321	100%

Around 38% of the respondent VDCS were 30 to 50 years old whereas 44% of the VDCS were less than 20 years old.

(d). VDCS Gender Wise Distribution of Milk Producer Members:

Gender of Milk Producer in the VDCS	Total No. of Respondents	Gender (%)
Male	48586	58%
Female	34944	42%
Total	83530	100%

There are around 58% of male farmer members in the selected VDCS.

(e). VDCS Gender of VDCS Secretary:

Gender of VDCS Secretary	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	333	92%
Female	30	8%
Total respondents	363	100%

Around 92% of VDCS Secretary were male.

(f). Age group of VDCS Secretary/Chairman:

Age group of VDCS Secretary/Chairman	No. of Respondents	Percentage
20-29	16	4%
30-39	115	32%
40-49	128	35%

50-59	86	24%
>=60	18	5%
Total	363	100%

As indicated in the above table, around 71% of the VDCS Secretary were in the age bracket of less than 49 years. Also 36% of the VDCS Secretary were in the age bracket of less than 39 years. This can be considered as fairly young age group.

(g). Educational Qualification of VDCS Secretary / Chairman:

Level of Education	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Illiterate	1	0%
Upto 9th Std.	70	19%
SSC	136	37%
11th Std.	21	6%
HSC	73	20%
UG	56	15%
PG	6	2%
Total	363	100%

Most of the VDCS chairman/ Secretary were literate. More than 37% of the respondents had educational qualification of HSC and Higher.

(h). Employment Status of VDCS Secretary/Chairman:

Employment Status of VDCS Secretary/ Chairman	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Unemployed	264	73%
Employed in Central government	2	1%
Employed in State Government	7	2%
Employed in Private	90	25%
Total	363	100%

It can be seen from the above table that 28% of the VDCS Secretary/ Chairman were employed and 73 % were unemployed.

(i). Main occupation of VDCS Secretary/ Chairman:

Main Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Dairy	23	6%
Dairy + Farming	241	66%
Farming only	0	0%
Dairy/ Farming + employed	99	27%
Total	363	100%

The main occupation of VDCS Secretary /Chairman was Dairy + Farming. (around 66% of the total respondents)

(j). VDCS Milk Collection:

Milk Collection / Member (In Liters)	No. of VDCSs	Percentage
0-3.0	117	32%
3.1-6.0	115	32%
6.1-9.0	54	15%
9.1-12.0	27	7%
12.1-15.0	12	3%
15.1-18.0	4	1%
>18.0	34	9%
Total	363	100%

The above table indicates that around 64% of the VDCS members poured milk less than 6 litres per day.

(k). VDCS List of Equipment:

The following equipment/ instrument/systems were available at majority of the VDCs

1	Automated Milk Collection System (AMCS)
2	Bulk Milk Coolers (BMC)

3	Weighing Meter
4	Automatic Fat Tester/ Milcotester
5	Lactometer
6	Can
7	Computer

(l). Number of computers in VDCS:

No. of Computers	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	296	82%
2	56	15%
3	5	1%
4	4	1%
>4	2	1%
Total	363	100%

All VDCS were having computer facility at their offices.

(m). VDCS Do You Give Incentive for Quality:

Do You Give Incentive for Quality	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	179	49%
No	184	51%
Total respondents	363	100%

VDCS were not able to mention the type of incentive.

(o). VDCS Details of Training Taken by Your Staff:

	Year 2012	Year 2013	Year 2014
S.No	No. of VDCS that had sent their staff in Training	No. of VDCS that had sent their staff in Training	No. of VDCS that had sent their staff in Training
1	23	23	22

The above table indicates that around 23 staff members of VDCS were sent for various training programs in a given year. This number is very small when compared with the total number of respondent VDCS (363 VDCS).

(p). VDCS Have a BMC:

Do You Give Incentive for Quality	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	159	44%
No	204	56%
Total respondents	363	100%

Only 44% of the respondents had BMC facility.

4. Conclusion:

From the above analysis it can be concluded that most of VDCS of Gujarat state are registered and have Young and literate employees and are well equipped with ICT facility available in terms of computers. However, few VDCS are not ISO certified and do not have Bulk Milk Chilling (BMC) facility and in the era of women empowerment, the issue of less female representation in management of VDCS should be addressed. Issues like capacity building and Training on Record keeping should be looked into. Overall it can be said that the VDCS of the state have contributed significantly to the development of Dairy Sector in the state.

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